

A Study to Assess the Impact of Job Stress on Physical Health Status, Quality of Life and Experienced Illness among Professional Drivers at Vijayapur City, with an View to Provide an Information Booklet

Geetanjali Bagewadi¹, Savitri Katti², Dr Ningangouda Patil³, Ambika Gadalotti⁴, Avinash Kajagar⁵

^{1,4,5}“ 4th Yr B. Sc[N], BLDEA’s Shri B M Patil Institute of Nursing Sciences-Vijayapur-Karnataka”

²“Asst Professor BLDEA’s Shri B M Patil Institute of Nursing Sciences-Vijayapur-Karnataka”

³“Prof Dept of Child health Nursing BLDEA’s Shri B M Patil Institute of Nursing Sciences-Vijayapur-Karnataka”

Abstract:-

➤ Background

Because this job is a part of public service field/sector. Bus-drivers are physically and psychologically get stressed.factors in the working environment that cause stressful situations and negative health consequences of the workplace stress. In short, health outcomes of professional drivers working under highly demanding conditions can be summarized in terms of both physical and mental illnesses, such as: ergonomic complications associated with physical working conditions. respiratory and gastrointestinal disorders, eye problems, lung cancer related to the prolonged exposition to contaminant and toxic gasses, sleep problems and chronic fatigue. Psychological distress and several mental health disturbances such as anxiety, and depressive disorders, have health related adverse working conditions, workplace stress and burnout of various occupational groups to both adverse psychological health indicators (such as the psychological distress measured by the short form of Goldberg’s GHQ-12) and negative lifestyle outcomes.

➤ Aim

The aim of this study was to determine whether or not there is a relationship between health-related quality of life and work related stress and to explore if socio- demographic characteristics have an influence on this relationship.

➤ Methodology:

- **Research approach :** Quantitative research approach
- **Research Variables:** In this study research variables are quality of life, job stress, physical health status and perceived illness.
- **Sampling technique:** The sampling technique used for the study was purposive sampling technique.

- **Sample size:** Sample for the study would consist 189. with confidence level 95%,approximate population – 370, population proposition – 50%, margin error-5%

Data was collected by using demographic profile, self structured questionnaire on quality of life , job stress and physical health status

➤ Results :

The data gathered were summarized in the master sheet and both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis. In overall findings reveals that Level of stress mean Value is 142.65 mean value is 118 range of score is 175-85 so that Sd Value is 5.93 R value is -0.201 got p-value is 0.005549 and Quality of life of drivers mean value is 115.18 and median value is 164 and range pf value is 174-106 so got the Sd value 12.48. p-value is 0.005549 So the Hapothesis co-relation is accepted between the stress and quality of life among professional drivers Findings revealing the presence of significant difference between stress and quality of life among professional drivers.

I. OBJECTIVES

➤ Objectives Achieved:

- To assess the level of job stress, physical health status, quality of life and experienced illness among professional drivers.
- To find the co-relation between job stress and quality of life among professional drivers.
- To find the association between job stress, physical health status quality of life scores with selected demographic variables.

➤ *Field/ Experimental Work Giving Full Details of Summary of Methods Adopted Supported by Necessary Tables, Charts, Diagrams and Photographs.*

II. STUDY DESIGN AND APPROACH

➤ *Materials and Methods of Study:*

- *Source of data:* The data will be obtain from KSRTC drivers.
- *Research approach :* Quantitative research approach
- *Study Setting:* The study will be conducted in selected KSRTC bus stand of Vijayapur city.
- *Population:* The population of the study will be KSRTC Drivers
- *Research Variables:* In this study research variables are quality of life, job stress, physical health status and perceived illness.

➤ *Methods of Data Collection*

- *Sampling technique:* The sampling technique used for the study was purposive sampling technique.
- *Sample size:* Sample for the study would consist 189. with confidence level 95%, approximate population – 370, population proposition – 50%, margin error-5%

➤ *Inclusion Criteria:*

- Drivers from KSRTC department
- KSRTC Drivers from vijayapur city
- Those who all are willing to participate in this study

➤ *Exclusion Criteria:*

- Drivers from private sectors.
- Drivers from other than vijayapur city

➤ *Instrument Intended to be Used:*

- Job stress Scale: is used to assess the job stress among KSRTC drivers.
- Physical health status: will be assessed by measure BP, Height, weight, calculation of BMI, waist circumference,
- Quality of life: will be assessed by using WHO quality of life scales.
- Experienced illness: will be assessed by checklist.

➤ *Data Collection Method:*

- Permission will be obtained from the concerned authority.
- The purpose of the study will be explained to participant.
- Getting informed consent.
- The questionnaire will be administer to the drivers.
- Assess the health status by vital status and BMI among Drivers
- The data will be analyzed and interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics.
- At last giving information booklet.

III. STEPS OF DATA COLLECTION

➤ *Data Analysis Plan:*

Data was analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Table1 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Drivers According to Age in Years.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Age in years		
<40	114	60.3
>40	75	39.7

Fig 1 clustered Column Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Drivers According to Age in Years.

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to age in years, 114(60.3%) were in <40, and 75(39.7%) were in >40 age in years.

Table 2 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Drivers According to Educational Status.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Primary	15	7.93
High School	94	49.74
PUC	65	34.39
Others	15	7.94

Fig 2 Clustered Column Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Drivers According to Educational Status.

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to educational status, 15 (7.93%) were in the primary education, 94(49.74%) were in the high school education, 65(34.39%) were in the PUC and graduation, and 15(7.94%) of them were in the other group.

Table 3 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Religion.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Religion		
Hindu	138	73.01
Muslim	30	15.87
Christian	13	6.88
Others	8	4.24

Fig 3 Clustered Column Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Religion.

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to religion 138(73.01%) were Hindu, 30(15.87%) were muslim and 13(6.88%) were Christian and 8(4.24%) were others.

Table 4 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Years of Experience in Driving

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
Years of experience	f	%
5 Years	18	9.52
5-10 Year	33	17.46
10-15 Years	50	26.45
15 Years	88	46.57

Fig 4 Clustered Column Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution Of Driver’s According To Years Of Experience In Driving

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Years of experience in driving 18(9.52.%) were having 5years of experoence, 33(17.46%) were 5-10 Years and 50(26.45%) were 10-15 Years and 88(46.57%) were 15 Years of experience.

Table 5 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Languages Known.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
Languages Known	f	%
Kannada	127	67.19
Hindi	36	19.06
English	44	7.4
Marathi	11	5.83
others	1	0.52

Fig 5 Clustered Column Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Languages Known.

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Languages Known 127(67.19%) were knowing Kannada, 36(19.06%) were knowing Hindi and 44(7.4%) were knowing English and 11(5.83%) were 15 knowing Marathi and1(0.52) were knowing other language.

Table 6 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Income Status

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Income status		
15,000	20	10.58
15,000-20,000	26	13.75
20,000-25,000	35	23.8
More than 25,00	98	51.87

Fig 6 Clustered Column Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Income Status

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Income status 20(10.58%) were earning 1500/- 26(13.75%) were earning 15,000-20,000/- , 35(23.8%) were Earning around 20,000-25,000/- and 98(51.87%) were Earning more than 25,000/-

Table 7 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Marital Status

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Marital status		
Married	147	77.77
Unmarried	22	11.64
Divorsed	15	7.94
Widow/Widover	5	3.65

Fig 7 Pie Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Marital Status

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Marital status 147(77.77%) were Married 22(11.64%) were Unmarried, 15(7.94%) were Divorced and 5(3.65%) were Widover.

Table 8 depicting percentage wise distribution of Driver’s according to Accidental History.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Accidental History		
Yes	75	39.68
NO	84	44.45
If yes, How many times	15	9.5
More than two times	12	6.34

Fig 8 Pie Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Accidental History.

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to accidental History 75(39.68%) were Having accidental History. 84(44.45%) were not having Accidental history, 15(9.5%) were having Accidental history within two times, and 12(6.34%) were having more than two times of accidental history,

Table 9 Epicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Source of Income.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Sources of Income		
Driving only	125	66.13
Driving + Business	36	20.04
Driving +Others	28	13.83

Fig 9 3d Pia Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Source of Income.

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Source of Income 125(66.13%) were doing only driving. 36(20.04%) were doing driving + business 28(13.83%) were doing driving+other work.

Table 10 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Location of Living.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Location of living		
Urban	57	30.15
Rural	94	49.73
Sub Urban	32	16.93
slums	6	3.19

Fig 10 3d Pia Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Location of Living.

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Location of living 57(30.15%) were living in urban area. 94(49.73%) were living in rural area, 32(16.93%) were living in sub urban area and 6(3.19) were living in slum area .

Table 11 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Working Day Per Month.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Working day per month		
15 days	14	7.43
15-20 days	36	19.04
20-25 days	57	30.15
25 days	82	43.38

Fig 11 Clustered Column Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Working Day Per Month.

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to working day per month 14(7.43%) were working 15days. 36(19.04%) were working 15-20 days, 57(30.15%) were working 20-25 days and 82(43.38%) were working 25days.

Table 12 Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Activity to Relaxing Mind.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Activity to relaxing your mind		
Watching TV	14	7.7
Reading newspaper	36	19.04
Chit chatting	57	30.15
Using Mobile	82	43.11
Other	0	0

Fig 12 Clustered column diagram depicting percentage wise distribution of Driver’s according to activity to relaxing mind.

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to activity to relaxing mind 14(7.7%) were relaxing mind by watching TV, 36(19.04%) were relaxing their mind by reading newspaper, 57(30.15%) were relaxing their mind by chit chatting and 82(43.11%) were relaxing their mind bu using mobile,

Table 13 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Types of Family

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Types of Family		
Nuclear	51	50
Joint	79	30
Extended	59	20

Fig 13 Clustered Column Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Types of Family

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Types of family 51(50%) were belongs to nuclear family, 79(30%) were belongs to joint family and 59(20%) were belongs to extended family.

Table 14 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver’s According to Types of Diet

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Types of Diet		
Vegetarian	75	39.68
Egg vegetarian	43	22.75
Mixed	67	35.45
Other	4	2.12

Fig 14 Clustered Column Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver's According to Types of Diet

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Types Diet 75(39.68%) were belongs Vegetarian, 43(22.75%) were belongs to Egg vegetarian, 67(35.45%) were belongs to mixed diet and 4(2.12%) were belongs to other pattern of diet.

Table 15 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver's According to Habits

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Habits		
Alcohol	47	24.86
Cigarratte Smoking	28	14.82
Tobacco	59	31.22
Others mentioned	55	29.10

Fig 15 Clustered Column Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver's According to Habits

The above table and fig shows that Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Habits 47(24.86%) were use to have alcohol, 28(14.82%) were cigarratte smokers , 59(31.22%) were tobacco chiwing 55(29.10%) were mentioned othe

Table 16 Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver's According to Daily Average Driving.

Demographic Variables	Group (N=189)	
	f	%
Daily average driving		
100 KM	30	15.88
200-300 KM	24	12.69
300-400 KM	38	20.10
400 KM	97	51.13

Fig 16 Clustered Column Diagram Depicting Percentage Wise Distribution of Driver's According to Daily Average Driving.

The above table and Fig Shows the Percentage wise distribution of the subjects according to Daily average driving 30(15.88%) were use to drive daily 100 KM, 24(12.69%) were use to drive daily 200-300 KM , 38(20.10%) were use to drive daily 300-400 KM 97(51.13%) were use to drive daily 400 KM.

Table 17 Co-relation between Socio-demographic Variables With Stress and Quality of Life

SI NO		Mean	Median	Range	SD	r	P-value	Significance
1	Stress	142.65	118	175-85	5.93	-0.201	0.005549	significant
2	QOL	115.18	164	174-106	12.48			

As table (17) shows that Level of stress mean Value is 142.65 mean value is 118 range of score is 175-85 so that Sd Value is 5.93 R value is -0.201 got p-value is 0.005549 and Quality of life of drivers mean value is 115.18 and median value is 164 and range pf value is 174-106 so got the Sd value 12.48. p-value is 0.005549 So the Hapothesis co-relation is accepted between the stress and quality of life among professional drivers Findings revealing the presence of significant difference between stress and quality of life among professional drivers.

Table 18 Association between SDV With Experienced Illness

SI NO	Demographic Variables	d.f	Chi square value	Table value	P. Value	Significance
1	Age	1	0.104	3.89	0.7474	N.S
2	education	3	2.485	7.89	0.4780	N.S
3	Religion	3	6.013	7.89	0.1109	N.S
4	Years of experience in Driving	3	1.511	7.89	0.9797	N.S
5	Languages Known	4	3.084	9.49	0.5438	N.S
6	Income per months	3	47.26	7.89	<.0001	Significant
7	Marital status	3	9.01	7.89	0.2915	Significant
8	Accidental History	2	9.6	5.99	0.0500	N.S
9	Sources of Income	3	5.92	7.89	0.1155	N.S
10	Location of living	3	3.957	7.89	0.2661	N.S
11	Working day per month	3	4.134	7.89	0.2473	N.S
12	Activity to relax your mind	3	7.991	7.89	0.660	N.S
13	Types of Family	3	6.327	7.89	0.967	N.S
14	Types of Diet	2	2.762	5.99	0.251	N.S
15	Habits	3	5.714	7.89	0.126	N.S
16	Daily average driving	3	1.573	7.89	0.665	N.S

Table 18 Chi square test was used to find the association between the socio-demographic variables and Experienced Illness among drivers. No significant association was found between the Experienced Illness among drivers and their socio-demographic variables are: age 0.104(0.7474) education 2.485(0.4780) , religion 2.485(0.1109), years of experience 1.511 (0.9797), languages3.084 (0.5438), Accidental History 9.6 (0.0500),Sources of Income 5.92(0.1155) ,Location of living

3.957 (0.2661) , Working day per month 4.134 (0.2473), Activity to relax your mind 7.991 (0.660), Types of Family 2.762 (0.251), Types of Diet, Habits 2.762 (0.251), Daily average driving 1.573 (0.665).

And there is a Significant association was found between the Experienced Illness among drivers socio-demographic variables: Income per months 47.26 (<.0001), and marital status 9.01 (0.2915). at 0.05 lvl of significance.

Table 19 Association between SDV With Quality of Life

SI NO	Demographic Variables	d.f	Chi square value	Table value	P.Value	Significance
1	Demographic Variables	1	24.361	3.84	0.00001	Significant
2	Age	3	29.63	7.89	0.00001	Significant
3	education	3	2.817	7.89	0.420709	NS
4	Religion	3	4.738	7.89	0.192019	NS
5	Years of experience in Driving	4	57.56	9.49	0.00001	Significant
6	Languages Known	3	13.645	7.89	0.00343	Significant
7	Income per months	3	4.126	7.89	0.24876	NS
8	Marital status	2	0.71	5.99	0.701173	NS
9	Accidental History	3	47.88	7.89	0.00001	Significant
10	Sources of Income	3	15.019	7.89	0.0018	Significant
11	Location of living	3	2.011	7.89	0.570127	NS
12	Working day per month	3	6.533	7.89	0.8837	NS
13	Activity to relax your mind	3	2.668	7.89	0.445693	NS
14	Types of Family	3	25.561	7.89	0.000012	Significant
15	Types of Diet	3	1.9767	7.89	0.577257	NS
16	Habits	3	2.021	7.89	0.56806	NS
	Daily average driving					

Table 19, The above table shows that , there is no association between Quality of life among drivers the socio demographic variables as religion 2.817 (0.420709), years of experience 4.738 (0.192019), marital status 4.126(0.24876), accidental history 0.71(0.701173), working day per month 2.011(0.570127), activity to relax mind 6.533 (0.8837), types of family2.668 (0.445693) , habits 1.9767 (0.577257) daily average of driving 2.021 (0.56806). are not having significant towards quality of life.

And there is a significant variables with quality of life among drivers . the demographic variables are Age 24.361 (0.00001), education 29.63 (0.00001), Languages Known 57.56 (0.00001), Income per months 47.88(0.00343), Sources of Income 47.88 (0.00001), Location of living 15.019 (0.0018),Types of Diet 25.561 (0.000012). at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 20 Association between SDV With Stress

SI NO	Demographic Variables	d.f	Chi square value	Table value	P.Value	Significance
1	Demographic Variables	1	18.617	3.84	0.000016	Significance
2	Age	3	18.77	7.89	0.000305	Significance
3	education	3	0.377	7.89	0.944952	N.S
4	Religion	3	13.012	7.89	0.004611	Significance
5	Years of experience in Driving	4	18.47	9.49	0.000999	Significance
6	Languages Known	3	12.27	7.89	0.006513	Significance
7	Income per months	1	0.5	3.84	0.918891	N.S
8	Marital status	2	58.79	5.99	<0.0001	Significance
9	Accidental History	3	3.173	7.89	0.365713	N.S
10	Sources of Income	3	32.36	7.89	<0.0001	Significance
11	Location of living	3	4.667	7.89	0.197869	N.S
12	Working day per month	4	2.852	9.49	0.58289	N.S
13	Activity to relax your mind	2	2.091	5.99	0.351526	N.S
14	Types of Family	1	1.39	3.84	0.238405	N.S
15	Types of Diet	3	0.605	7.89	0.890287	N.S
16	Habits	3	15.62	7.89	0.001357	Significance
	Daily average driving					

Table 20 Chi square test was used to find the association between the socio- demographic variables with Stress of Drivers. No significant association was found between the Stress and their socio-demographic variables are: religion 0.377 (0.944952), Marital status 0.5 (0.918891) Sources of Income 3.173(0.365713), Working day per month 4.667(0.197869), Types of Family 2.091 (0.351526), Types of Diet 1.39 (0.238405), and habits 0.605 (0.890287). And there is a Significant association was found in their Socio-demographic variables are: age 18.617(0.000016) ,

education 18.77 (0.000305) years of experience 13.012(0.004611) , Languages 18.47 (0.000999), Income status 12.27 (0.006513), location 32.36 (<0.0001), accidental history 58.79 (<0.0001), Daily average driving 15.62 (0.001357) at 0.05 level of significance. there is a significant variables with quality of life among drivers . the demographic variables are Age 24.361 (0.00001), education 29.63 (0.00001), Languages Known 57.56 (0.00001), Income per months 47.88(0.00343), Sources of Income 47.88 (0.00001), Location of living 15.019 (0.0018),Types

of Diet 25.561 (0.000012). There is a significant of Quality of life will be the T-value is 0.201 it is 0.05 level of significant association with With Experienced Illness variables are Income per months 47.26 (<.0001), and marital status 9.01 (0.2915). there is a Significant association was found in their Socio-demographic variables are: age 18.617(0.000016) , education 18.77 (0.000305) years of experience 13.012(0.004611) , Languages 18.47 (0.000999), Income status 12.27 (0.006513), location 32.36 (<0.0001), accidental history 58.79 (<0.0001), Daily average driving 15.62 (0.001357) at 0.05 level of significance. there is a significant variables with quality of life among drivers . the demographic variables are Age 24.361 (0.00001), education 29.63 (0.00001), Languages Known 57.56 (0.00001), Income per months 47.88(0.00343), Sources of Income

IV. RESULT

The data gathered were summarized in the master sheet and both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis. In overall findings reveals that out of 189

There is a significant of Quality of life will be the T-value is 0.201 it is 0.05 level of significant association with With Experienced Illness variables are Income per months 47.26 (<.0001), and marital status 9.01 (0.2915). there is a Significant association was found in their Socio-demographic variables are: age 18.617(0.000016) , education 18.77 (0.000305) years of experience 13.012(0.004611) , Languages 18.47 (0.000999), Income status 12.27 (0.006513), location 32.36 (<0.0001), accidental history 58.79 (<0.0001), Daily average driving 15.62 (0.001357) at 0.05 level of significance. there is a significant variables with quality of life among drivers . the demographic variables are Age 24.361 (0.00001), education 29.63 (0.00001), Languages Known 57.56 (0.00001), Income per months 47.88(0.00343), Sources of Income 47.88 (0.00001), Location of living 15.019 (0.0018),Types of Diet 25.561 (0.000012).

V. CONCLUSION

This chapter presents the conclusions drawn, implications, limitations, suggestions, and recommendations. The main focus of this study was **to assess the impact of job stress on physical health status, quality of life and experienced illness among professional driver at vijayapur city.** The data was collected from 189 samples.

Chi square test was used to find the association between the socio- demographic variables with Stress of Drivers. No significant association was found between the Stress and their socio-demographic variables. and their sociodemographic variables are: age, education, religion, Years of experience in Driving, Languages Known, Income per month, Marital status, Accidental History, Sources of Income, Working day per month, Activity to relax your mind, Daily average driving,

There is no significant association was found between the Experienced Illness among drivers and their socio-demographic variables are: age, education, religion, Years of experience in Driving, Languages Known, Income per month, Marital status, Accidental History, Sources of Income, working day per month, Activity to relax your mind, Daily average driving,

Findings revealing the presence of significant difference between stress and quality of life among professional drivers at vijayapur district.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We Acknowledge Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences-Bangalore for releasing the grant for conducting research study. We extend our heartfelt gratitude to KSRTC Manager and staffs, workers for providing conducive environment for successful completion of study. And also to beloved Principal for their constant support and guidance for completion of research work.

Conflict of Interest:- None declared

Ethical Clearance:- Ethical clearance certificate was obtained by institutional ethical committee.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Paisley K, Powell GM. A study of job stress and burnout and related factors in the hospital personnel of Iran 2016 Jul; 8(7): 2625–2632. Published online 2016 Jul 25. doi: 10.19082/2625
- [2]. Rajib Lochan Dhar. A study was conducted on stress among government city bus drivers in Hubli from 4th June to 3rd July 20 The Journal of International Social Research; 2008:1/5 fall.
- [3]. **PeerJ 6(3):e6249** Work stress and health problems of professional drivers: A hazardous formula for their safety outcomes. **December 2018 PeerJ 6(3):e6249** DOI:10.7717/peerj.6249 Project: Job stress, burnout, health and traffic safety of public transport drivers Alonso F, Esteban C, Useche S, Serge A. 2017b. Perception of the impact of certain health conditions on driving performance. Public Health International 2(1):1–7
- [4]. SUTTLE C 1977. Stress and its effects on psychological health of the bus drivers. Journal of emerging technologies and innovative research (JETIR) www.jetir.org560.